

Training Methods in Cross-Cultural Human Resource Development: An intercultural study

Vilmante Kumpikaite^{a *}

^a*Kaunas University of Technology, Laisves al. 55, Kaunas 44309, Lithuania*

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to present trainings methods evaluation's differences according to students' country. The sample of this study is conducted on 721 students in Lithuania, Iran, Turkey, and Spain in 2011. The obtained data from the questionnaires are analyzed through the SPSS statistical packaged software. Results of empirical research showed that Spanish students prefer group learning the most. However these methods are the least developing for Turks and Iranians. They prefer one-to-one learning methods, as well as Lithuanians. Generalizing we could suggest that it should be taken in to account these different altitudes of students in different countries when teaching and working with them.

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Keywords: Human Resources, Cross – Cultural Human Resource Development, Human Resource Training Methods, Culture, Students

1. Introduction

Cultural and social contexts vary leading to varied human resource development practices. Therefore human resource development as a discipline needs to develop a globally accepted definition for international human resource development to accommodate the extensive amount of cross-national human resource development work that is being done by transnational corporations, transnational nongovernmental organizations, and transnational political entities.

Looking to this broader context of research that explores concepts and theories of the field in a cross-cultural context, it is likewise important to look at a definition of human resource development that may not fit in the context of a specific culture or in a specific national environment, but rather relates to how we understand the field when it is applied in an international or cross-national context.

Speaking about human resource training and development practices in different regions of the world, several scholars and international experts view different countries within a region as more homogeneous; others view them as more heterogeneous (Ronen and Shenkar, 1985; Dirani, 2006).

Nowadays students are more international than they were few decades ago. However, students from different countries represent different attitudes and behavior still. It is important for enterprises to see differences of X, Y and Z generations, especially Y and Z, because they are future employees and employers. Therefore, empirical study research of this paper was done exploring students.

Culture influences every aspect of human resource development. All authors provide such factors as culture and it is a matter of central importance for cross - national HRD. Diagnosing and understanding learners' cultural values is as important as understanding their training needs. In this paper authors analyse factors impacting human resource development in cross-cultural context.

The purpose of this paper is to present training methods of students by cross-cultural human resource development.

* Vilmante Kumpikaite . Tel.: +370-37-300-571

E-mail address: vilmante.kumpikaite@ktu.lt

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Methods of the research are analysis and synthesis of the scientific literature and empirical research based on questionnaire. The empirical research is based on theoretical background and presents investigation of students' skills developing factors and differences according to students' nationality in Spain, Lithuania, Turkey, and Iran. A survey was carried out by distributing questionnaire, which was designed and tested for this purpose earlier (Kumpikaite (2009)). Individual, one –to-one and group training methods are selected based on analyzed scientific literature for this survey.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Definition of Cross – Cultural Human Resource Development

Several definitions and frameworks of human resource development (HRD) were offered throughout the history. Nadler coined the term human resource development in 1970 and offered a model with three components: training, education, and development (Nadler and Nadler, 1991). Much of the published literature on the definition of the field has been focused in the west—originally, in the United States (Weinberger, 1998) and, increasingly, in Europe. However, human resource development is a discipline that is more developed in Western industrialized countries than the rest of the world. Therefore, defining HRD is not easy and up till now no single point of view or framework of HRD has been predominant (Dilworth, 2003). Weinberger (1998) explored the different HRD definitions in the United States and concluded that there is no one agreement on definition of the field and that HRD is rather a mosaic of multiple perspectives.

Speaking about broader context of research that explores concepts and theories of the field in a cross-cultural context, it is likewise important to look at a definition of human resource development that may not fit into the context of a specific culture or in a specific national environment, but rather relates to how we understand the field when it is applied in an international or cross-national context.

One of the major barriers to creating a definition of cross – national HRD is that HRD has evolved differently in different nations. HRD practitioners from different nations use culturally based perceptions and attitudes to define their work and its effectiveness that often varies from U.S. - based HRD definitions. As cultural and social contexts vary leading to varied HRD practices, HRD as a discipline needs to develop a globally accepted definition for IHRD to accommodate the extensive amount of cross-national HRD work that is being done by transnational corporations, transnational nongovernmental organizations, and transnational political entities.

Wang and McLean (2007) keep international HRD, cross-national HRD, transnational HRD, and global HRD as synonyms and give us such definition:

“International HRD (also known, perhaps more appropriately, as cross-national HRD, transnational HRD, and global HRD) is a field of study and practice that focuses on for-profit, not-for-profit, and/or governmental entities and individuals cooperating in some form across national borders. The purpose of this interaction is systematically to tap existing human potential and intentionally shape work-based, community-based, society-based, culture-based, and politically based expertise through multiple means for the purpose of improving cross-national relationships collaboratively across all involved entities through greater mutual understanding, improved individual and organizational performance, improved standards of living and quality of life, reduced conflict between entities and individuals, and any other criteria that would be deemed useful by the involved entities”.

Cross – cultural preparation is very important for successful HRD (Noe, 2005). It involves educating employees and their family members who were sent or emigrated to a foreign country. To successfully conduct business in the global marketplace, employees must understand the business practices and the cultural norms of different countries.

Variations in HRD practices and systems are directly linked to the socio-cultural variations among countries and regions around the world (Dirani, 2006).

Many cultural characteristics influence employee behavior. Keep in mind that there are national cultures as well as company cultures. A culture refers to the set of assumptions that group members share about the world and how it works and the ideas worth striving for (Sathe, 1985). Culture is important because it influences the effectiveness of different behaviors and management styles.

Hofstede (1991) believes that national culture is the strongest influence on the behavior of employers and employees, customers and citizens – stronger than differences in professional roles, education, age, or gender. Laurant (1983) discovered that the impact of culture was greater in global companies than in domestic ones, that a multinational environment causes people to cling even more strongly to their own cultural values.

To be successful in overseas companies, foreign employees need to be:

- Competent in their area of expertise.
- Able to communicate verbally and nonverbally in the host country.
- Flexible, tolerant of ambiguity, and sensitive to cultural differences.
- Motivated to succeed, able to enjoy the challenge of working in other countries, and willing to learn about the host country’s culture, language, and customs.
- Support by their families (Arthur and Bennett, 1995; Garonzik et al, 2000).

Summarizing, we can state that culture is a matter of central importance for cross-cultural HRD. Variations in HRD practices and systems are directly linked to the socio-cultural variations among countries and regions around the world (Dirani, 2006).

2.2. Training methods

Looking in employees’ skills development we can speak about different types of training. These methods could be developed in accordance of their techniques as traditional and modern computer based methods or number of people involved in learning process. Following training methods based on Noe (2005), Mankin (2009), Kumpikaite and Sakalas (2007, 2008) analyzed methods are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Training (learning) methods

Individual or self-learning methods are such, which allow trainees to learn alone, independent from others. One-to-one learning methods are such methods when a trainee is involved to the learning process together with other person, which could be a teacher or other trainee too. Group learning methods are such methods when several participants are involved in to learning process. Group methods are described as the best developing methods (Kumpikaite and Ciarniene, 2008 a,b). Therefore we can see that there are a lot traditional (as Lectures, Groups projects, Discussions and others) as well as modern (E-learning or Learning networks) group learning methods.

3. Empirical study and its results

3.1. Introduction of study and sample

A survey was carried out by distributing questionnaires, which was designed and tested for this purpose earlier (Kumpikaite, 2009).

Besides cultural dimensions, trainers must consider language differences in preparing training materials. Cultural adaptation is as crucial to achieving results as is language translation. Therefore language aspect is very important for our explored students because they are from countries that do not speak native English. Without this cultural sensitivity, little or no learning will occur. If an interpreter is used, it is important to conduct a practice session with the interpreter to evaluate pacing of the session and whether the amount of topic and material is appropriate. Original questionnaire was prepared in Lithuanian. Questionnaires were prepared in respondents' native languages for this study. Therefore, original research instrument was translated in to English later, using double translation method for checking, and given to Turkey, Spain and Iran, where it was translated in to these languages and set out for survey. The questionnaires were given throw Internet in Lithuania, Turkey and Spain, and printed questionnaires were distributed in Iran (Kumpikaite et al., 2012).

The study was conducted in Lithuania (203 respondents), Turkey (162 respondents), Spain (125 respondents), and Iran (196 respondents) in 2011. Total 377 females and 303 males participated in this poll. Students had to select 3 the most developing factors, where the most developing was evaluated by 3, the second by 2 and the third -1. The main questions formulated in this study were:

- (1) What skills' training methods do students evaluate the best and the worst? and
- (2) What are differences among students' answers in cross-cultural context?

General information about respondents is given in Table 2.

Table 1. Respondents information according gender and country

Groups	Iran	Lithuania	Spain	Turkey	Total
Missing	3	0	0	3	6
Female	90	138	81	68	377
Male	103	65	44	91	303
Total	196	203	125	162	686

According to Figure 2 we can see very different results of evaluation. Team work gets one of the highest evaluation and the lowest difference among countries' answers. Summarizing, we can say Lithuanians, Turks and Iranians are most developed by one-to-one learning methods, but Spanish prefer group learning at the same time. However these methods are at least developing for Turks and Iranians.

Comparative analysis of pair countries was made and no statistical difference among training methods between Turkey and Iran was found. Statistical significant differences were found between other countries. None Spanish evaluation was better than Lithuanians. However, Spanish are more developed by distance training and worse by watching training programs, instructions of others, development courses and Reading literature in comparison with Turks. Spanish are more developed by distance training and project performing and worse by watching training programs, instructions of others, development courses, reading literature and considering tasks with supervisor measuring them with Iranians. Lithuanians evaluated their skills development by reading special literature, considering of received task with supervisor and development courses better than Spanish. However Lithuanians are more developed by distance training and considering of received task with supervisor Instructions of others and worse by reading of educational literature, and Instruction of others than Turks. Moreover, Lithuanians are more developed by project performing, special tasks, distance training and considering tasks with supervisor and worse instruction of others, and reading literature comparing with Iran.

Figure 2. Means of training methods by countries

4. Conclusion

Culture is very important in working with people and developing them. So it is very important to pay attention to such factors as language, cross-cultural communication, religion, family, class structure, geography and history.

Results of our empirical research showed that Spanish prefer group learning the most. However these methods are the least developing for Turks and Iranians. They prefer one-to-one learning methods, as well as Lithuanians. It could be related with respondents' culture. Empirical study also showed that learning methods differ on respondents' gender a bit. Females are more developed by special tasks, and distance training and less by instructions of others than males.

All received results could be useful for professors teaching students and for every person identifying their weak sides and necessity to develop skills. Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA) (Human resource development, 2005) suggests focusing on achieving seven skills providing cross-cultural training program: Communicate respect, Be non-judgmental, Personalize knowledge and perceptions, Display empathy, Practice role flexibility, Demonstrate reciprocal concern, Tolerate ambiguity.

However it should be noted that more detail research is needed to look at students' used development methods as study conditions are various in different classes and different countries and students face with different teachers and methods.

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